

Presence of Formaldehyde in the Terrestrial and Solar Atmospheres.

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In a recent communication (*Nature*, 1932, 130, 313) we have reported that freshly collected rain water contains appreciable amounts of formaldehyde. In the months of June, July, August, and September, 1932, we analysed numerous samples of rain water and estimated quantitatively the amounts of formaldehyde present per litre of freshly collected rain water by the well known iodine method. We have observed that the amount of formaldehyde varies from 0.00015 g. to 0.001 g. per litre of rain water. We have found that the quantity of formaldehyde present in a particular sample of rain water becomes exceedingly small, if it is collected after a very heavy shower. In order that appreciable amounts of formaldehyde may be detected in a sample of rain water, the rain water should be collected after some sunny days and it should be analysed immediately after collection.

It is well known that carbonic acid and water vapour exist in the atmosphere and under the influence of ultraviolet light from the sun, they should combine and form formaldehyde and oxygen. Hence it seems probable that formaldehyde should be present in the atmosphere. If appreciable amounts of formaldehyde were present in the atmosphere, it should be partially washed down with rain water.

It is generally believed that hardly any radiation from the sun shorter than 2900\AA is available on the earth's surface. Moreover, it is assumed that a very thin layer of ozone (3 mm. when reduced to 760 mm. pressure) formed in the atmosphere at higher altitudes, is capable of absorbing solar radiations shorter than 2900\AA . This ozone is supposed to be formed by the absorption of shorter radiations by the oxygen of the atmosphere.

As a result of absorption measurements various physicists notably Fabry and Buisson (*Astrophys. J.*, 1921, 54, 297; Mecke, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, 29, 375), Dobson (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1930, A 129, 411) and others have concluded that the mean altitude of the ozone layer in the atmosphere is about 50 kilometers.

Our experimental observations on the existence of formaldehyde in rain water show that it is present in the upper layers of the atmosphere. We are of the opinion that this formaldehyde is formed in the atmosphere as a result of the photochemical combination of carbon dioxide and water vapour present in the atmosphere under action of ultraviolet rays from the sun. It will be interesting to note that Lob (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1906, 12, 282) reported to have obtained only traces of formaldehyde on passing a silent electric discharge in moist carbon dioxide, but Lunt (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, A 108, 172) is of opinion that α -particles, β -rays and the corona discharge in carbon dioxide and water vapour do not cause the formation of formaldehyde or formic acid.

It is well known that the reaction,

requires ultraviolet light of wave-length 2550 Å. In this connection it should be noted that we have shown in this laboratory that very seldom all the active rays are absorbed by an absorbing solution and hence it appears that all short ultraviolet rays coming from the sun will not be absorbed by the ozone layer present in the atmosphere. Some of the short-wave radiations are likely to pass through the ozone layer and decompose water into H and OH and these hydrogen atoms may reduce CO_2 to formaldehyde. This reduction of carbon dioxide by atomic hydrogen appears to be accelerated by the action of short-wave radiations. The heat of dissociation of water into H and OH is 110,000 calories. In other words, the energy required in the formation of a gram mole of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water is practically the same as that required in the breaking of the H—OH link. As the energy requirements of both the reactions are the same, it appears that the chemical change involved in carbon assimilation is the photo-decomposition of water into H and OH. It appears that the function of chlorophyll and carotinoids present in leaves is that of a photo-sensitiser as well as that of a reducing agent helping the photo-reduction of carbonic acid. But the chief chemical change in photosynthesis appears to be the photolysis of water into H and OH by the absorption of energy of the sun.

In recent years the existence of free OH radical has been postulated by numerous workers. Thus Haber and his collaborators (*Z. Physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 137, 263; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1930, 36, 711), Hinshelwood (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, A 118, 170) and Frankenburg (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, 27, 431) have advanced the view

that OH radicals are formed in the combination of hydrogen and hydrocarbons with oxygen. Similarly the existence of OH has been assumed in the chain mechanism involved in the photochemical combination of chlorine and hydrogen in presence of moisture. Very recently, Franck and Haber (*Ber. Berl. Akad.*, 1931, 250), Haber and Wansbrough-Jones (*Z. Physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **18B**, 103), Farkas and Wansbrough-Jones (*ibid.*, 124) and others have suggested that not only in photochemical reactions taking place in aqueous solutions but also in catalytic and enzyme reactions OH radicals play an important rôle. It has been postulated that in many photochemical reactions taking place in aqueous solution, the primary change is the photolysis of water into H and OH. The secondary reactions are believed to take place between the atomic hydrogen and the OH radicals and the other substances present in the system.

It appears, therefore, that the mechanism of the formation of formaldehyde in the atmosphere is the same as that taking place in plants, the first stage being the photochemical decomposition of water into H and OH. Very recently Henri and Schou (*Z. Physik*, 1928, **49**, 744) and Herzberg (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, **27**, 378) have measured the *ultraviolet* absorption of formaldehyde vapour and they are of opinion that the absorption spectra extend from 3700 Å to 2500 Å and that there are about 35 to 40 bands between 2500 Å and 3700 Å. The maximum absorption at 2935 Å is characteristic of aldehydes.

It is apparent, therefore, that not only ozone but also formaldehyde present in the atmosphere absorbs short rays of the solar radiations. Hence the absorption of solar radiations shorter than 2900 Å which has been so far attributed to the presence of ozone may be partially due to the formaldehyde present in the atmosphere. Formaldehyde in the atmosphere may also be decomposed under the influence of light. Recent experiments of Norrish and Kirkbride (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1518) show that the main products of the photochemical decomposition of formaldehyde are carbon monoxide and hydrogen. It is evident, therefore, that the following equilibrium

may exist in the atmosphere. It is well known that the upper atmosphere is rich in hydrogen. Consequently due to the presence of hydrogen, the photo-decomposition of formaldehyde will be markedly

hindered and appreciable amounts of formaldehyde can exist in the atmosphere.

The following lines in the solar spectrum are attributed to the presence of OH group in the absorbing atmosphere of the sun. The OH lines in the solar spectrum may be due to the presence of OH formed from the photo-decomposition of water as depicted below :

Wave-length.	Intensity.	Wave-length _s	Intensity.
3267·063	1	3147·448	1
3255·498	1N	3146·935	1
3238·554	-1	3146·599	1
3233·670	-1	3145·527	0
3229·884	0	3139·165	2
3226·447	-1	3137·897	-1
3218·076	-1	3136·891	1
3213·475	-1	3136·591	0
3210·725	-1	3134·338	1
3210·481	1	3131·447	0
3210·047	0	3130·568	1
3209·435	-1	3123·777	-1
3206·239	0	3128·522	0
3203·981	1	3127·098	-1
3202·698	0	3126·618	1
3202·258	-1	3124·919	2
3200·963	1	3123·260	1
3193·055	-1	3123·444	-1
3191·800	-1	3122·571	2
3189·318	0	3122·220	0
3188·060	1	3117·770	1
3181·991	3	3117·202	1
3181·642	-1	3117·038	-1
3180·492	0	3114·779	1
3179·967	-1	3114·629	-1
3177·681	1	3113·098	-1

Wave-length.	Intensity.	Wave-length.	Intensity.
3175·315	1	3106·033	2
3174·381	0	3105·678	1
3174·491	1	3104·350	-1
3172·998	1	3103·285	0
3169·862	0	3102·149	1
3169·617	0	3101·243	1
3168·956	1	3099·576	0 N
3167·178	1	3099·417	1
3166·336	0	3098·589	2
3164·549	0	3096·625	0
3161·902	0	3096·139	2
3158·522	0	3095·348	3
3157·502	1	3094·627	2
3156·846	0 N	3094·470	-1
3152·958	0	3093·609	-1
3152·458	-1	3092·404	1
3151·006	1	3091·372	1
		3091·214	1 N
3090·869	0	3077·028	0
3090·487	0	3075·136	0
3090·375	1	3074·386	1
3089·869	2	3072·183	0
3089·746	2	3071·146	1
3089·001	0	3070·493	1
3087·454	0	3070·381	-1
3087·346	1	3069·916	1
3086·230	0	3069·182	2
3085·207	2	3068·797	0
3084·898	1	3068·599	1
3084·056	-1	3068·282	1
3083·283	1	3067·658	1
3081·551	1	3064·956	1

Wave-length.	Intensity.	Wave-length.	Intensity
3081·248	2	3064·217	2
3080·246	0	3063·556	3

These lines have been obtained from the publication of St. John, Moore, Ware, Adams, Babcock (*Carnegie Institution of Washington*, 1928).

Moreover, hydrogen also escapes in the air from the occluded gases inside the earth and in marshy places. Also it can come to the atmosphere from the probable photo-decomposition of hydrocarbons like CH_4 , C_6H_6 and of H_2S , etc. It is well known that ammonia exists in the earth's atmosphere. Moreover, Fowler and Gregory (*Phil. Trans.*, 1919, **A218**, 351) have concluded from spectroscopic evidence that ammonia is present in the absorbing atmosphere of the sun. It is generally believed that cyanogen gas is also present in the solar atmosphere.

Recently Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, **206**, 270) has shown that several unidentified lines in the solar spectrum agree fairly well with the absorption spectra of formaldehyde vapour. Hence it has been concluded that formaldehyde may also form one of the ingredients present in the absorbing atmosphere of the sun. Moreover, it appears that free hydroxyl group is also present in the solar atmosphere.

What is the origin of these substances in the solar atmosphere? Very little is known about this point. In view of the various facts cited above, it is not at all surprising that formaldehyde is present both in the solar and the earth's atmosphere.

Further work in this line is in progress and we are trying to find out whether there is a relation between the incidence of thunderstorms and the amount of formaldehyde in the atmosphere.

SUMMARY.

1. Formaldehyde is present in rain water to the extent of 0·00015 g. to 0·001 g. per litre of freshly collected rain water.

2. It appears that the energy required in the formation of formdehyde from carbon dioxide and water vapour is the same as that required in the breaking of the H—OH link and the first stage in photosynthesis is the photo-decomposition of water into H and OH.

3. The formation of formaldehyde in the terrestrial atmosphere and in plants appears to be due to the reduction of carbon dioxide by the atomic hydrogen formed from the photolysis of water.

4. Several absorption lines in the solar spectrum are attributed to the existence of OH radical and formaldehyde in the absorbing atmosphere of the sun.

5. The decomposition of formaldehyde is hindered by the presence of hydrogen in the atmosphere.

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